

Exploring the Effectiveness of Parental Assistance Versus Technological Assistance in Improving Emotional Intelligence and Communication in Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder

Ishika Korla

Valley Christian High School, San Jose, CA, U.S.A

ABSTRACT

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) accounts for a broad scope of disorders that affect social, communicative, and language skills, which all range in severity depending on the individual. Low levels of emotional intelligence in children with ASD contribute to the primary deficiencies in communication and relationships that define the disorder. Studies have shown growing evidence for interventions using traditional reading approaches with parental assistance and technological interventions as effective ways to combat shortcomings in emotional intelligence and communication in children with ASD. Taking into account the traditional way of reading with parental assistance, parents can take steps to learn various strategies to produce positive results in their child's linguistic development and engagement. On the other hand, implementing novel technological interventions such as robots, applications, and serious games can improve a child's social skills, communication skills, and empathy.

Keywords: *ASD, Children, Technology, Parental-assistance*

1. INTRODUCTION

Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) face many challenges in the development of social skills, communication skills, and emotional intelligence (Ploog et al., 2012). While children with ASD tend to exhibit impairment mainly in these three attributes, each child with the disorder experiences varying levels of severity. The extent of this impairment plays a significant role in how their language abilities develop (Charman et al., 2005). Deficiencies in

communication skills tend to include difficulties in interpreting language, such as issues with pragmatics and incomprehension or misconceptions regarding speech (Grynszpan et al., 2008). Comprehension and production abilities, the child's ability to produce words and proper language, become indicators for communication development later on, making the years up to preschool especially critical for children with ASD (Weismer & Kover, 2015). These primary deficiencies in communication and relationships result from low levels of emotional intelligence (EI), a type of social intelligence that accounts for the ability to manage one's own emotions as well as the feelings of others. The scope of EI includes verbal and non-verbal emotion, emotional regulation, and problem-solving as impacted by emotions (Petrides et al., 2011; Wilkinson, 2013). Both communication skills and emotional intelligence influence the social skills of children with ASD, affecting the lifestyle and behavior of these children. Impaired socialization as a result of restricted communication in children with ASD is closely related to their difficulties in peer interaction and disorderly behavior in social settings, which tend to isolate children (American Psychiatric Association, 1994).

With emerging advanced technologies, there is a stronger focus on services for children with ASD (Ploog et al., 2012). One such service includes program applications such as computer-assistive technology (CAT) programs, which utilize sound and visual features to improve deficiencies in communication, emotional recognition, social skills, and theory of mind (the recognition of the mental health of oneself and others) (Ploog et al., 2012). If implemented correctly, CAT programs have the potential to provide high levels of precise and practical training in strengthening the skills of children with ASD (Ploog et al., 2012). In addition to CAT programs, more refined socially assistive robots can be vital to improving social skills and deficiencies in cognitive abilities by providing different types of interactions and using simulations (Vélez & Ferreiro, 2014; Cho & Ahn, 2016). These robots implement essential techniques such as imitative abilities, body movements, facial expressions, and audio to achieve their purpose (Cho & Ahn, 2016; Bakola & Drigas, 2020). Games focused on education and learning skills can build upon the enjoyment children with ASD gain from playing games (Kapp, 2012). The predictability and structure provided by technology grant children with ASD a sense of ease, making games an optimal choice to help teach skills to this community (Wojciechowski & Al-Musawi, 2017). Serious games target emotion recognition, promoting emotional

production and social skills by providing collaborative opportunities and working on behaviors in social situations (Grossard et al., 2017). While these technologies hold great potential in aiding the development of children with ASD, each faces fundamental limitations. Due to the diverse set of situations children with ASD face, CAT programs can be rendered ineffective at encapsulating everything necessary for a specific child, especially when considering the varying levels of deficiencies one child with ASD might have compared to another (Ploog et al., 2012). Similarly, while robots could play an essential role in improving the lives of children with ASD, more research should be conducted before researchers label robots as the safest, most optimal form of intervention (Bakola & Drigas, 2020). Although serious games have increased over the years and work toward aiding children with ASD, all face limitations to some extent (Grossard et al., 2017).

As opposed to using the technological approach to grow social skills, communication skills, and emotional intelligence in children with ASD, the traditional method takes a more personal approach with a stronger emphasis on the role of parents. A parent's communication with their child can play a significant role in their linguistic development, especially for children with ASD (Haebig et al., 2013). Such types of verbal input from parents include techniques termed “follow-in commenting” and “follow-in directives,” which facilitate linguistic learning for children through joint attention (Haebig et al., 2013; Adamson et al., 2004). Other essential parent responses incorporate linguistic mapping, parents verbally expressing something the child cannot articulate, repetition, and expansions of what the child is saying (Haebig et al., 2013). Specific parent-based interventions, such as Naturalistic Development Behavior Interventions (NDBIs) and Shared Reading, display the significance of a parent’s role (Schreibman et al., 2015; Akemogly et al., 2020; D’Agostino et al., 2020). Parents can also utilize additional strategies and techniques, such as combinations of shared reading and naturalistic teaching, an intervention type called Parent-Implemented Communication Strategies-Storybook (PiCSS), to enhance communication in children with ASD (Akemoglu & Meadan, 2019.)

Additionally, parent involvement can be effective in managing emotional regulation in children with ASD. Researchers noted that when a parent exhibited positive behavioral phenotypes, such as affection, toward the child, the child responded with increased positive behavior (less

disorderly and aggressive) (Boeldt et al., 2012; Maljaars et al., 2014). One significant technique in developing a child with ASD's EI is emotional or motivational scaffolding, which plays a crucial role in a parent's attempt to motivate emotional growth in their child through parent co-regulation (Gulsrud et al., 2010). While parental assistance serves as an effective measure in helping children with ASD, whether it is more or less effective than technology remains unknown based on the limited information available. Both measures of intervention serve to aid development in children with ASD, and different approaches work differently for each child. This report will discuss the differences between the effect of parental assistance and technological uses on the development of social skills, communication skills, and emotional intelligence in children with ASD.

2.1 Effectiveness of reading with parental assistance on improving EI and social/communication skills

A parent's interactions with their child can be meaningful in developing language skills for children with ASD (Haebig et al., 2013). Lack of gestures, deficiencies in language comprehension, lack of increasing complex vocalizations, and lack of recognition or response towards their name are all aspects that have been observed (during infancy) in these children through home videotapes (Bates et al., 1991; Mitchell et al., 2006; Osterling & Dawson, 1994). Signs of delays in communication and language for children with ASD can appear as early as 12 months of age and account for delays in gestures, difficulty in responses, and lack of word production (Mitchell et al., 2006). These early signs serve as indicators of the abilities the child maintains in their preschool years and are often predictors of the individual's language development in the future (Howlin et al., 2000). Due to the importance of fostering language skills in the early years of children with ASD, parent intervention, specifically verbal input, is significant in aiding this development (Haebig et al., 2013; McDuffie & Yoder, 2010; Siller & Sigman, 2002).

Parents can utilize various types of verbal input to foster linguistic skills in children with ASD (Baldwin, 1995; Tomasello & Farrar, 1986). One such type of verbal input from parents has been termed the phrase “follow-in commenting,” where parents provide commentary and labels

that align with the child's scope of interest to facilitate linguistic learning for children with ASD and decrease mapping and cognitive errors (Haebig et al., 2013; Adamson et al., 2004). This verbal input from parents can be crucial in fostering joint attention, which plays a significant role in developing a child with ASD's linguistic abilities (Adamson et al., 2004; Luyster et al., 2008). Another parental input called "follow-in directives" can be classified into two categories - follow-in directives for language and follow-in directives for behavior - which prompt children to respond communicatively or behaviorally (Haebig et al., 2013). Unlike follow-in commenting, follow-in directives elicit a response from the child and don't just simply maintain their attention (Siller & Sigman, 2008). Although there is limited research on these two techniques, current studies show a positive correlation between the implementation of follow-in commenting and follow-in directives with improvements in language (McDuffie & Yoder, 2010; Haebig et al., 2013). Parent responses include linguistic mapping (when parents put something the child cannot articulate into words), repetition, and expansions (Haebig et al., 2013). The study done by Haebig and colleagues on parent language input reinforces the notion that parents' specific verbal language inputs produce positive results in the linguistic development of children with ASD (2013).

Along with verbal cues, parents play a significant role in Naturalistic Development Behavior Interventions (NDBIs), which support the natural learning of children with ASD in specific contexts (Schreibman et al., 2015; Akemoglu & Tomeny, 2020). Such naturalistic teaching is particularly influential in teaching day-to-day life skills to those with social impairments (Schreibman et al., 2015). Similarly, when used by parental figures, naturalistic communication teaching (NCT) strategies have also been shown to increase social communication skills (Dubin & Lieberman-Betz, 2019; Biggs & Meadan, 2018). Some particularly beneficial NCT strategies include modeling (demonstration of words/responses), mand-model (firm verbal requests), and time delay (eliciting communication through a stimulus) (Akamoglu & Meadan, 2019). Furthermore, the Parent-implemented Communication Strategies-Storybook (PiCSS), a combination of naturalistic teaching and shared reading, utilizes parents to implement NCT strategies and specific verbal cues to enhance communication in children with ASD (Akamoglu & Meadan, 2019). This combination of techniques has shown success, as one study revealed higher communicative responses from a child with ASD after parents increased the use of NCT

strategies (Akamoglu & Meadan, 2019). Moreover, shared reading, another crucial technique employed by caregivers that involves parents reading to the child and fostering involvement, positively impacts nonverbal and verbal communication skills in children with ASD by including interactive elements in the reading process (D' Agostino et al., 2018; Akemoglu & Tomeny, 2020). To gain more insight into the effectiveness of teaching parents reading techniques and NCT strategies, Akemoglu and Tomeny conducted a study revealing that such an intervention is effective as all families involved showed satisfaction and noted considerable progress in communication and engagement (2020).

Not only is parental intervention influential in impacting social and communicative manners in children with ASD, but parents can also have a profound effect on emotional regulation in their children (Ting & Weiss, 2017). Parental behavior towards or in the view of children with ASD significantly correlates with their child's behavior as more positive parental behaviors are associated with fewer behavior problems, while more controlling parental behaviors are associated with higher behavior problems (Boeldt et al., 2012; Maljaars et al., 2014; Boonen et al., 2014). Due to the close ties between parental emotion and the emotions of the child with ASD, parents must step in as “co-therapists” or take a more significant part in portraying certain emotions and coping strategies for their child (Sofronoff et al., 2005; Reaven, 2010). A parent's relationship with their child with ASD is a substantial aspect of the social-emotional development of the child (Mendoza, 2022). As the caregiver, parents must be able to balance the role of parenting along with the responsibility of handling the child's emotions with sensitivity (Mendoza, 2022). A crucial technique parents use to support their child with ASD is motivational or emotional scaffolding, which is the ability to maintain the involvement and enthusiasm of the child throughout an activity and make said activity enjoyable (Hoffman et al., 2006). This act by parents to motivate the child through emotional scaffolding and similar strategies is termed parent co-regulation and aims to enhance the development of EI in the child (Gulsrud et al., 2010). Parents play a monumental role in increasing EI and social and communicative skills by emphasizing interaction and critical strategies.

2.2 Effectiveness of technological assistance in improving EI and social/communication skills

As technological influence has increased in recent years, researchers have placed greater regard on utilizing these technological developments for children diagnosed with ASD (Bakola & Drigas, 2020; Brooks et al., 2012). One such area of beneficial technological advancement is the utilization of social robots (Bakola & Drigas, 2020). Social robots, or more specifically, Socially Assistive Robots (SAR) and Socially Interactive/or Intelligent Robotics (SIR), can be key to improving social skills and cognitive deficits in children with ASD by providing multiple forms of interactions and using simulation (Cho & Ahn, 2016). Such robots implement motor skills, including imitation, facial expressions, body movements, and gestures (Bakola & Drigas, 2020). In addition to these skills, researchers have designed robots to emphasize appearance and the use of audio, including songs and voices (Bakola & Drigas, 2020). For instance, the therapeutic robot Kaspar, developed by Dautenhahn and colleagues, functions to assist in enhancing communication and social interaction skills for children with ASD by using imitative abilities, body movements, and limited expressions through its more petite, more childlike frame (Vélez & Ferreira, 2014; Robins et al., 2018; Miller, 2018). While social robots generally focus on encouraging social interaction, some are more specialized in certain aspects than others (Yousif et al., 2019; Tucker, 2015). For example, the robot Leonardo aims to boost social interaction for children with ASD but emphasizes using socio-cognitive abilities to model empathy to achieve this goal (Bakola & Drigas, 2020).

Similarly, the robot Zeno prioritizes using expressive face and body movements. In contrast, the robot Milo plays a more significant role in fostering empathy in children with ASD through expressive iPad-controlled face and camera receptors for targeting emotional feedback. (Yousif et al., 2019; Tucker, 2015). A study by Goodman validates the effectiveness of the robot Milo for children with ASD, finding that children were more involved with the robot than with a physician (2017). Although these therapeutic and humanoid robots are only a few examples, they showcase the immensely beneficial abilities of the robots and convey that Artificial Intelligence and social robots can play a critical role in safely helping children with ASD (Bakola & Drigas, 2020).

In addition to robots, technologies used for programs and applications can play a fundamental role in aiding children with ASD (Ploog et al., 2012). Due to the complexity of disorders that

encompass ASD, adaptive and adjustable learning is essential for children with the disorder, and technological advances over the past several years have allowed computer-assistive technologies (CAT) to help this community (Ploog et al., 2012). CAT programs demonstrate promise in improving deficiencies in language, emotional recognition, social skills, and communication skills in children with ASD (Bernard-Opitz et al., 2001; Ploog et al., 2012; Colby, 1973). To increase efficiency in these areas, CAT programs such as TeachTown: Basics and Baldi utilize animation, audio, and visuals to target weaknesses (Whalen et al., 2010; Bosseler & Massaro, 2003; Massaro & Bosseler, 2006; Williams et al., 2004). The TeachTown: Basics program aims to reduce negative behaviors while promoting positive communication and speech through self-paced lessons that employ animated reward games (Whalen et al., 2006). Likewise, Baldi implements visuals as talking heads, promoting improvements in speech and communication with feedback (Massaro, 2006; Ploog et al., 2012). Furthermore, such programs are more accessible to administer as CAT treatments are entirely digital and can reach broader demographics, including those with less money to spare for expensive treatments (Ploog et al., 2012; Ploog, 2010; Goodwin, 2008). The predictability and structure provided by technology grant a sense of ease for people with ASD. This reassurance makes technological applications such as MOSOCO, which uses a mobile device camera to help improve social skills, optimal choices to help teach skills to this community (Escobedo et al., 2012). Such programs operate with sensors, virtual/ augmented reality, geolocation, virtual agents, and Kinect to help aid the ASD community, including children, in developing specific skills (Valencia et al., 2019). Additionally, applications such as ABRACADABRA target language skills and focus on improving the understanding of expressions, thoughts, and feelings in the form of words (Arciula & Bailey, 2019). Other applications focus entirely on social skills, targeting communication and emotion (Valencia et al., 2019). While technological applications have their limitations and require more research in most cases, this area of technological advancement has the potential to benefit the lives of children with ASD (Ploog et al., 2012).

Lastly, this paper will discuss serious games that help children with ASD. Two scopes of focus affected by serious games can be defined (Grossard et al., 2017). Serious games are designed to counteract deficiencies in emotional recognition and social skills (Grossard et al., 2017). Serious games target emotional recognition by implementing pictures, drawings, and audio/video

recording, with visuals followed by audio being the most frequent stimuli (Vannetzel et al., 2011; Grossard et al., 2017). Along with emotional recognition, some games, such as LifeIsGame, promote emotional production by having users mimic models (Fernandes et al., 2011). Serious games tend to be diverse, with variations among games (Grossard et al., 2017). Two such games relating to EI that showcase this diversity are CopyMe, which includes three levels focusing on producing facial expressions and having users mimic them, while the next game, JeStimule, focuses on recognition of expressions in different social situations using two modes (Tan et al., 2013; Serret et al., 2014). In addition to games targeting emotional recognition and production, serious games also target social skills, primarily collaborative skills and behaviors in social situations (Grossard et al., 2017). Serious games that emphasize developing social skills tend to focus more on collaboration and communication between the children rather than having them complete the game individually (Grossard et al., 2017). One game that focuses on strengthening communication skills is the Cooperative Puzzle Game, which uses a multi-user screen to encourage collaboration (Battocchi et al., 2008).

Additionally, serious games may employ virtual environments that model public situations or prompt interactions with virtual characters (Grossard et al., 2017). Virtual environments allow children with ASD to better develop their empathy through social situations that foster collaboration and prompts that call for reflection on the child's emotions (Cheng et al., 2010). While serious games do still face restrictions on their capabilities, they present the possibility of successfully aiding children with ASD in enhancing social skills and EI.

2.3 Impact of reading with parental assistance vs using technological assistance

Both parental and technological assistance present benefits that positively impact the community of children affected by ASD. In order to evaluate which is more effective, this paper will consider the strengths of both. One study by Haebig and colleagues reinforces the parent and child linguistic relationship, focusing on “follow-in commenting” and “follow-in directives” (2013). It defines the relationship between parent language input that follows in the child’s focus of attention and parent language input that reacts to child communication. Through 15-minute play sessions in which parents played with children, the study supported that parents' specific

verbal language input produced positive results in the language development of children with ASD (Haebig et al., 2013). Additionally, another study by Akemoglu and Tomeny investigated the effectiveness of teaching parents reading techniques and NCT strategies and their impact on communication skills in children with ASD (2020). The study implemented a multiple-baseline design and recorded data through observations and social validity interviews to measure the effectiveness of these techniques and strategies through this parent-reliant intervention (Akemoglu & Tomeny, 2020). The results revealed this intervention to be effective, as all families involved showed satisfaction and noted considerable progress in communication and engagement (Akemoglu & Tomeny, 2020).

On the other hand, technological assistance also presents promising potential in aiding children with ASD in developing crucial skills. As discussed in greater detail, studies present social robots as solid examples of technological resources that help develop social skills, verbal communication, and empathy in children with ASD (Bakola & Drigas, 2020). The social robot Milo, which has already shown success in initial results, is one specific instance of the promising success of robots and technology (Mills, 2017). Furthermore, the increase in the number of research papers, 74% being case studies, exploring the usefulness of technology for children with ASD shows the expanding presence of technology in becoming an influential component of care for children with ASD (Valencia et al., 2019). At times, applications have been successful, as seen with the ABRACADABRA application investigated by Arciuli and Bailey (2019). Through the ABRACADABRA application, the researchers compared raw scores using ANOVA pre and post-instruction and found significant development in word and passage reading accuracy (Arciuli & Bailey, 2019). Researchers have also seen this statistically shown success in serious games, such as the prototype presented in a study by Khowaja and colleagues, in which they used the single-subject research design (SSRD) to measure the effectiveness of the prototype on the vocabulary of children with ASD (2018). The results of the study revealed that the prototype did play a role in improving the vocabulary of children with ASD, as correct responses were produced in fewer attempts and shorter time (Khowaja et al., 2018)

3. Conclusion

This paper focused on the review of parental and technological assistance in comparison to each other concerning the effects of each on children with ASD. Given the deficiencies in social skills, communication skills, and emotional intelligence that make up ASD, this paper concentrated on the impact of the two types of intervention in these main areas (Ploog et al., 2012). Parental assistance in aiding a child with ASD can have a significant impact on the child in improving crucial deficiencies in their development. Parents can implement specific strategies such as NCT strategies and types of parental input such as “follow-in commenting” and “follow-in directives” to facilitate the development of social and communication skills in a child with ASD (Haebig et al., 2013; Adamson et al., 2004; Dubin & Lieberman-Betz, 2019; Biggs & Meadan, 2018). Furthermore, parental involvement can be significant in assisting the development of EI in children with ASD, given the close relationship between parents and children’s emotions as well as the use of techniques such as motivational and emotional scaffolding (Gulsrud et al., 2010; Boeldt et al., 2012; Maljaars et al., 2014). While studies displaying the effectiveness of parental involvement with their child with ASD have shown the advantages of parental assistance, parental assistance does face limitations. If not executed properly, a parent can also have a negative effect on the behavior and development of their child with ASD (Boeldt et al., 2012).

In contrast, technological assistance, including robots, applications, and serious games, has also shown effectiveness in interventions and studies as the field grows. SAR and SIR utilize a multitude of skills and assets to encourage advancement in empathy and social and communicative skills (Cho & Ahn, 2016). Various applications also include specific design choices and facilities to boost growth in these three areas. Similarly, serious games emphasize user experience to target the development of specific skills (Valencia et al., 2019). These technologies also face restrictions in their abilities, with calls for better clinical validity and additional research to ensure effectiveness (Grossard et al., 2017).

Given that parental and technological assistance presents advantages and drawbacks, choosing a better option is difficult. As there is limited information on which holds a more significant influence in aiding children with ASD, there is no decisive conclusion. Depending on the child and what works best for them, one path might be more or less effective. Parental involvement provides a more personal approach and may be more effective for a child who benefits from

in-person interaction or is high-functioning. Given that the field of technological advancements for children with ASD is still emerging and advancing, the traditional approach of parental assistance is a reliable, safe option. However, technological approaches could be much more influential for a child with a higher affinity for video games and computers. To determine which approach is feasible for a specific child, one must consider the parent's ability to make time for a parental assistive approach and their financial situation to afford a technological approach. Each family's situation is unique, and it is the parent's job to help their child find the intervention best suited for their and the family's needs.

4. Limitations

The limitations of parental assistance and technological assistance in influencing the development of skills and behaviors in children with ASD also need to be considered alongside their strengths. If parental involvement in the life of a child with ASD is dysfunctional and lacks purposeful care, it can be further detrimental to the child (Crowell et al., 2019). Additionally, when assisting their child with ASD, parents need to be particular about managing their own emotions in front of the child since parents' emotions can affect their child's behaviors (Zhou & Yi, 2014). Due to this, parental assistance requires further effort and stress on the parents' part, making it a more draining endeavor for the parents (Derguy et al., 2015). Similarly, parents' stress correlates with the severity of ASD in a child and the child's behavioral outburst, creating a stressful experience for parents trying to assist children who experience a high severity of ASD (Pozo & Sarriá, 2014). Although becoming educated on topics of ASD and available support around them can aid parents in lowering stress levels, if this education is not sought out or attained, it leaves families right where they started (Pozo & Sarriá, 2014). The added time to care for a child with ASD makes it harder for parents to access this education as well. Parents of children with ASD also face additional financial burdens and are required to dedicate a great deal of time to help support their children, which can make it more difficult for them to gain this education (DePape & Lindsay, 2015).

While CAT programs present significant benefits for children with ASD, some CAT programs do hold limitations (Ploog et al., 2013). For example, specific sound effects can set off children and

produce adverse behavioral effects. Poorly developed programs may further socially isolate the child and limit responses (Ploog et al., 2013). At this time, CAT is, at best, only a strong potential contender, rather than an absolute solution, in the treatment of ASD individuals (Coleman-Martin et al., 2005). Additionally, serious games have limits on clinical validation that prevent them from being a complete solution (Grossard et al., 2017). Further research focusing on current shortcomings such as in visuals, sample sizes, study durations, lack of control groups, and the limited utility of most games outside of high-functioning individuals with ASD is required (Grossard et al., 2017). Similarly, with robots, while researchers have found significant progress in children with ASD through social robots, further studies and research are recommended to solidify the effectiveness of this type of intervention (Bakola & Drigas, 2020). Furthermore, studies often do not consider user experience and accessibility in sufficient detail when developing technologies, even though these attributes are fundamental to the effectiveness of the technology (Valencia et al., 2019). Robots can also entail significant costs, being one of the more expensive technologies, and could be a resource out of reach for lower-income families (Kumm et al., 2022).

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